

Clinicopathological Study of Parotid Tumors in OdishaSiva Saumendra Sahoo¹, Sujit Kumar Mohanty², Abinash Kanungo³, Rakesh Kumar Ludam⁴, Nirod Kumar Sahoo⁵¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, DRIEMS Institute of Health sciences and Hospital, Tangi, Cuttack, Odisha, India²Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, SCB Medical College & Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha, India³Associate Professor, Dept of General Surgery, IMS & SUM Campus II, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, MKCG medical College & Hospital, Berhampur, Ganjam, Odisha, India.⁵Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, S.C.B Medical College & Hospital, Cuttack, Odisha, India

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Rakesh Kumar Ludam

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Salivary gland neoplasms are uncommon. Constitute 2-6.5% of all head and neoplasms and only 0.3% of all malignancies. About 64-80% of all primary epithelial tumors occur in parotid gland, 7-11% of the submandibular glands, less than 1% in the sublingual gland and 9-23% in the minor glands. 15-30% of tumors in the parotid gland are malignant in contrast to about 40% in the submandibular gland. Delayed presentation and malignant transformation invades facial nerve and causing facial palsy and becomes non-operable. 80% of parotid tumors are located in the superficial lobe. Deep lobe neoplasms are considered to have greater incidence of malignancy. Parotid tumors are not uncommon in Southern Odisha referred from various rural hospitals to M.K.C.G. Medical College & Hospital, Berhampur.

Aim: is to determine clinical / pathological variants of different parotid tumors presenting in M.K.C.G. Medical College & Hospital, Southern Odisha.

Method: 40 cases of parotid swelling admitted to this Hospital from 2021 to 2023. A prospective study was done with ethical clearance from ethical committee of M.K.C.G. Medical College & Hospital, Berhampur. All patients were evaluated with proper investigation like FNAC, X-ray of neck and parotid region, Ultrasonography of swelling, CT Scan & MRI of parotid swelling and neck were done. Surgery was done and all patients were asked for follow up routinely.

Observation: Benign tumors are more common in 20 to 50 years of age and malignancy tumors are common after 50 years. Male Female ratio is 1:2.6. In benign tumors M: F ratio is 1: 2.8 and in malignant tumors M: F ratio is 1: 2. Incidence of benign tumor is 85% and malignant tumor is 15%. Pleomorphic adenoma is the commonest benign tumor and mucoepidermoid carcinoma is the commonest malignant tumor.

Conclusion: Diagnosis Parotid gland tumors must be considered in any patient presenting with Parotid gland swelling. Swelling is the commonest symptom. The fact that mass has been present for several years is of no guarantee that it is benign. History and physical examination complementing FNAC help in diagnosis and has good accuracy in diagnosing parotid gland tumors. Surgery is the main modality of treatment in Parotid gland tumors.

Keywords: Parotid Tumors, Pleomorphic adenoma (PA), Mucoepidermoid Carcinoma (MEC), Facial palsy.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The Parotid gland is the largest (14 to 28gm) Salivary gland, which is derived from ectodermal layer of the oral cavity. Early in development of the salivary glands, the primitive duct buds are composed of inner lining of duct cells and an outer myoepithelial cell layer. Parotid gland developed 1st, beginning in 6th week of intrauterine life. An elongated furrow running dorsally from the angle of mouth

between the mandibular arch and maxillary process. No specific cause known for any benign or malignant tumor of salivary glands. There are certain cause like Genetic predisposition, Infective, Radiation, Smoking, Inflammation, Occupation and diet habit. Neoplasia is the result of disease of the reserve cells, which are responsible for tissue renewal, and not of the fully differentiated cells.

The genome of these cells contains the information needed to undergo normal development or to become a benign or malignant neoplasia. Malignant degeneration of normal differentiated cells does not occur.

About 64-80% of all primary epithelial tumors occur in parotid glands, 7-11% in the submandibular glands, less than 1% in the sublingual glands 9-23% in the minor glands [1]. In the files of Armed forces Institute of pathology [2]. (AFIP), about 1/3rd of major glands and half of minor gland tumors are malignant. 15-30% of tumors in the parotid gland are malignant in contrast to about 40% in the submandibular gland, 50% in the minor salivary gland and 70-90% of sublingual glands [3]. The ratio of malignant to benign tumor is greatest. (>2.3:1) in the sublingual gland tongue, floor of the mouth and retromolar area. [4]

The likelihood then of a salivary gland tumor being malignant is more or less inversely proportional to the size of the gland. [5,6]. These tumors usually occur in adults with a female predominance, but about 5% occur in children less than 16 years. [7] These tumors usually occur in adults with a female predominance but about 5% occur in children less than 16 years.

The incidence of parotid tumors is between 1-3/1lakh/year, approximately 75-85% of the salivary gland neoplasm occur in parotid of which 70-80% are benign and 80% benign tumors are pleomorphic adenoma. [8] FNAC of salivary gland tumors is advantageous to both the patient and the clinician because of its immediate results accuracy, lack of complication and economy [9].

Earliest reports of parotid extirpative surgery was recorded in Dutch literature of late 1600 [10]. This neoplasm was originally designated the benign mixed tumor in 1866 [11]. A name change to pleomorphic adenoma was 1st suggested in 1948. Papillary cystadenoma lymphomatosum was 1st described by Hildebrand in 1895.

The 1st case in English literature was reported by Nicholson in 1923 and in US was reported by Warthin in 1929 [12]. Mc Fairland (1930): Drew the attention to the high recurrence associated with enucleation [13]. The single lobe concept was documented and accepted with the understanding that a 'surgical' superficial lobe could be dissected away from the 'surgical' deep lobe maintaining the continuity and integrity of facial nerve during the dissection [14].

Aim and Objective: To determine clinical/pathological variants of different parotid tumors presenting in M.K.C.G. College & Hospital, Southern Odisha.

Materials and Methods

This prospective study of parotid gland tumors is based on 40 cases admitted in various surgical units in

M.K.C.G. Medical College and Hospital, Berhampur during the period from July 2021 to June 2023. A prospective study was done with ethical clearance from ethical committee of M.K.C.G. Medical College and Hospital, Berhampur, Odisha.

The statistics have been compared with different standard studies conducted on same subject by various authors around world.

Inclusion Criteria: All patient admitted to surgical wards in M.K.C.G. Medical College and Hospital with parotid gland tumors.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients who refused surgical treatment. Other salivary tumors other than parotid. And Parotid gland swellings other than tumors (inflammatory and non-inflammatory origin).

All patients admitted were evaluated by documenting the history, thorough clinical examination, routine laboratory investigation and specific investigation. Regarding physical examination, particular mentioned in the proforma was noted. Importance was given to the site, extent of the tumor, deep lobe enlargement and fixity to the surrounding structures, nerve involvement and regional lymphadenopathy.

Associated medical conditions like diabetes, hypertension and anemia were managed and controlled before surgery with physician's advice. Special investigations like FNAC, X-ray of neck and parotid region, USG of neck and parotid region, CT scan and MRI was done for some of these patients in the study group. Malignant tumors were referred to Radiotherapy Dept. M.K.C.G. Medical College and Hospital after surgery for post-operative radiotherapy. The adjuvant treatment was decided depending on the final Histopathological Report.

The follow up period of these patients for 6 months. All patients were asked for follow up after 15 days of surgery then every month for 6 months to detect morbidity and recurrence.

Figure 1: Patient with Parotid swelling

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used for analyzing the data using SPSS version 20 and results were presented in percentage and simple frequency.

Table 1: Distribution of Tumors in Different Age Group

Age in years	Benign tumors	Malignant tumors	Total Patients	Percentage
11 to 20	3	0	03	7.50%
21 to 30	10	0	10	25%
31 to 40	6	2	8	20%
41 to 50	10	0	10	25%
>50	5	4	9	22.50%
Total	34	6	40	100%

The age incidence of the patients in the study group ranged from 16-18 years. Most patients in this series were in the 3rd to 5th decade of life (70%). Benign tumors are more common in 20 to 50 years and malignancy tumors are common after 50 years. The mean age was 39 years for benign tumors and 58 years for malignant tumors.

Table 2: Tumor Sex Cross Tabulation

Sex	Benign	Malignant	Total	Percentage
Male	9	2	11	27.50%
Female	25	4	29	72.50%
Total	34	6	40	100%

In this series, 11 (27.5%) patients were male and 29 (72.5%) were female. M: F ratio is 1: 2: 6. In benign tumors M: F ratio is 1: 2: 8 and in malignant tumors M: F ratio is 1: 2.

Table 3: Symptoms of Salivary Gland Tumors

Symptoms	No. of Patients	Percentage
Swelling	40	100%
Pain	4	10%
Facial palsy	1	2.5
Recurrent tumor	4	10%

All patients presented with swelling. Features of rapid growth, pain and associated facial paralysis were considered as signs of malignancy. Out of 40 patients, 4 patients presented with pain (10%) in swelling, out of which 2 were benign and 2 were malignant. Pain occurred in 33% of the patients

with malignant tumors and 6% of the patients with benign tumors. One patient had facial nerve paralysis at presentation. 4 cases of recurrent tumor were operated in this series, out of which, 3 cases of Pleomorphic adenoma and one case of Mucoepidermoid carcinoma.

Table 4: Signs of Salivary Gland Tumors

Sign	Benign	Malignant
Fixity	0	2
Deep lobe involvement	1	1
Facial nerve involvement	0	1
Nodal involvement	0	2
Metastasis	0	0

Features of fixity, facial paralysis and nodal involvement were considered as signs of malignancy. Hard in consistency is noted mostly in malignant tumors. Deep lobe enlargement was seen in 2 pa-

tients in this series. 2 patients presented with cervical lymph node metastasis. 2 patients, one with malignant mixed tumor and other with MEC presented with fixity to masseter / mandible.

Table 5: Types of Surgical Treatment Adopted in the Study

Procedure	No. of cases	Percentage
Superficial parotidectomy	30	75%
Total parotidectomy	4	10%
Radical parotidectomy	1	2.5%
Excision	5	12.5%

Superficial parotidectomy was performed in 30 patients (75%), conservative total parotidectomy in 4 patients (10%) and radical parotidectomy in 1 patient.

Figure 2(b): Superficial Parotidectomy

Table 6: Complications Following Surgery

Complication	Benign tumors	Malignant tumors
Facial palsy – temporary	7	2
– Permanent	0	2
Salivary fistula	2	0
Frey’s syndrome	0	0
Recurrence	0	0
Wound infection	2	0

Post operatively 11 patients developed facial palsy, out of which 9 were temporary (improved over 3-6 months) and permanent facial nerve weakness occurred in 2 patients (5%), both of them had malignant parotid tumor. Wound infection occurred in 2

patients and parotid fistula occurred in 2 patients with pleomorphic adenoma who had undergone superficial parotidectomy, which healed spontaneously within 6 weeks. No postoperative death was encountered in this study.

Figure 3(a): Facial nerve Identification

Figure 3(b): Deep lobe involvement of Tumor

Table 7: Frequency of Cases Diagnosed By FNAC

Tumor	FNAC (+) ve		FNAC (-) ve	
	No.	%	No.	%
Benign	32	94%	2	6%
Malignant	5	83%	1	17%
Total	37	92.5%	3	10%

There is no statistical significant difference in accuracy in diagnosing benign and malignant tumor by using FNAC. In benign tumors, one case each of

benign myoepithelioma and benign lymphoepithelial lesion were interpreted as PA on FNAC. In malignant tumors acinic cell carcinoma was inter-

preted as PA FNAC. The exact overall cytohistological correlation was 92.5% and that of benign

and malignant tumors are 94% and 83% respectively.

Figure 4(a): Pleomorphic adenoma

Figure 4(b): Mucoepidermoid carcinoma

Table 8: Distribution of Various Types of Salivary Gland Tumors.

Tumor	No. Of Cases	% of total
Pleomorphic adenoma	26	65%
Warthin's	3	7.5%
Monomorphic	2	5%
Benign Lymphoepithelial tumor	3	7.5%
Mucoepidermoid tumor	3	7.5%
Acinic cell carcinoma	1	2.5%
Malignant pleomorphic	1	2.5%
Metastatic	1	2.5%

Overall pleomorphic adenoma constituted 65% of the tumor and among malignant tumor, mucoepidermoid carcinoma constituted 7.5% of the tumors in the series. Among the benign tumors, pleomorphic adenoma constituted 76.5% of the benign

tumors and among the malignant tumors, mucoepidermoid carcinoma constituted 50% of the malignant tumors.

Discussion

Table 8: Average Age Distribution of Salivary Gland Tumors in Various Studies

Series	Average age in years	
	Benign	Malignant
Potdur et.al (1969) [15]	40	49
Budharaj et.al. (1974) [16]	41	41
Mckenzie (1984) [17]	45	55

Skolnik et.al. (1977) [18]	45	56
Khazanchi et.al (1988) [19]	44	50
Renchan et.al (1996) [20]	55	59
Everson (1985) [21]	55	65
Present study	39	58

Analysis of the above data shows that, in most studies, benign tumor occurs at younger age group than malignant tumor.

Table 9: Sex Distribution of Salivary Gland Tumors in Various Studies

Series	Male	Female	Total	Ratio(M:F)
Fenn A.S. (1982) [22]	31	26	57	1.2:1
Everson et. al. (1985)	831	1579	2410	1:1.9
Renchan et.al. (1996)	652	542	1194	1.2:1
Seth, GSMC (1993-98) [23]	55	68	123	1:1.23
Present study	11	29	40	1:2.6

As per above data female preponderance noted in Everson et.al and GSMC studies which is comparable to the present study. Other studies showed male preponderance.

Table 10: Frequency of Benign and Malignant Salivary Gland Tumors in Various Studies

Series	No. Of Cases	Benign (%)	Malignant (%)
Eversole (1971) [25]	2513	79	21
Spiro R.H. (1986) [24]	2807	54.5	45.5
Ellis G. et.al. (1991) [26]	13749	63.2	36.8
Arathi Bhatia (1993) [27]	87	59.8	40.2
Renchan et.al. (1996) [20]	1194	80	20
Present study	40	85	15

In this study, benign tumors are more common than malignant tumors, similar to other studies.

Table 11: Comparison of Clinical Features

Sign / symptom	Spiro R.H. ²⁴ (1986)	Present Study
Swelling	100%	100%
Pain		
• Benign	4%	6%
• Malignant	10%	33%
Facial palsy	22%	2.5%
Cervical lymph node	23%	5%
Fixity to masseter/mandible	--	5%
Deep lobe involvement	--	5%

As per data shown swelling is the commonest symptom. Pain, facial palsy, lymph node involvement, fixity and deep lobe involvement suggests malignancy. Potdar.et.al have reported the incidence of pain and facial nerve paralysis in malignant neoplasms as 25-33% and 20-33% respectively.

Table 12: Frequency of Diagnostic Accuracy of Fnac in Various Studies

Series	Benign	Malignant
Frable and frable (1982) [28]	91%	92%
Spiro R.H. (1974) [29]	98%	93%
Present study	94%	83%

Diagnostic accuracy of FNAC is comparable to Frable and frable and Spiro R.H. studies for both benign and malignant.

Table 13: Comparison of Various Types of Surgery in Parotid Gland Tumors

Surgery	Leverstein H [30]	Present Study
Superficial parotidectomy	24.89%	77.5%
Partial superficial parotidectomy	53.86%	0%
Total parotidectomy	3.27%	10%

Superficial parotidectomy is commonest surgery done.

Table 14: Frequency of Salivary Gland Tumors in Various Studies

Series	Seth G.S. [23] (1993-98)	Jesus Souza et.al [31] (1987-97)	Present study
PA	64	34	26(65)
BCA	6	-	1
WT	1	8	3
M	2	2	1
MEC	5	11	3(7.5%)
ACC	2	--	1
ADCC	2	--	--
Undifferentiated Ca	--	1	--
Malignant Unspecified	1	--	--
Benign Parotid Tumor	42	--	3
CA Ex PA	--	3	1
Metastatic deposits	--	--	1

In the present study PA and MEC were the most common benign and malignant tumors respectively. These findings were similar to the previous studies.

Table 15: Permanent Facial Nerve Weakness

Source	Permanent facial weakness
JM Debetes & JDK Munting et.al. [32]	7%
Present study	5%

In this study, 5% (2in no.) of the patients developed permanent facial weakness, which is comparable to most of the western literature (1 patient with mucoepidermoid carcinoma and 1 patient with acini

cell carcinoma). Reported incidence of permanent facial weakness is 0-17%, as per western literature. Permanent facial weakness was 4% in both the series.

Table 16: Frequency of Postoperative Complications In Various Studies

Complication	Owen ERTC ³³ et.al.	Present Study
Facial palsy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temporary • Permanent 	38% 9%	22.5% 5%
Salivary fistula	2%	5%
Wound infection	--	5%
Frey's syndrome	11%	0%

Temporary facial nerve complication was the commonest complication in both studies.

Conclusion:

Following the study of 40 cases of major Salivary gland tumors diagnosis of Parotid gland tumors must be considered in any patient presenting with Parotid gland swelling. Parotid gland tumors occur more commonly in 3rd to 5th decade and seen most common in females. Parotid gland tumors are more often benign, pleomorphic adenoma. Swelling is the commonest symptom. History and physical examination complementing FNAC help in diagnosis. Surgery is the main modality of treatment in Parotid gland tumors. Most commonly done surgery is superficial parotidectomy. Since most alignant tumor is asymptomatic and longstanding benign tumor can undergo malignant change, community awareness and early referral are necessary.

References:

- Chan J, Cheuk W. Salivary gland tumors. In: Diagnostic Histopathology of Tumors. 4th edition. Philadelphia: Elsevier Health – US; 2013. P. 239-326.
- Batsakis JG. Pathology Consultation Carcinomas of the Submandibular and Sublingual Glands. Annals of Otolaryngology & Laryngology. 1986 Mar; 95(2): 211.
- Bhaskar SN, Bolden TE, Weinmann JP. Experimental obstructive adenitis in the mouse. Journal of dental research. 1956 Dec; 35(6): 852 – 62.
- Batsakis JG, Sneige N. Parapharyngeal and retropharyngeal space diseases. Annals of Otolaryngology & Laryngology. 1989 Apr; 98(4): 320 – 1.
- Silverberg SG, DeLellis RA, Auclair P, Ellis g. Major salivary glands. In: Silverberg's Principles and Practice of Surgical Pathology and

- Cytopathology. 3rd ed. Churchill Livingstone / Elsevier; 2006. P.1461- 1515.
6. Rosai J. Major and minor salivary glands. In: Rosai and Ackerman's Surgical Pathology 2 Volume Set. 9th edition. Edinburgh; New York: Mosby; 2004. P. 873 – 916.
 7. Young JA, editor, Salivary glands. In: Fine Needle Aspiration Cytopathology. 1st ed. Oxford; Boston: Blackwell Science Inc; 1993. P.48 – 67.
 8. Witt RL. The significance of the margin in parotid surgery for pleomorphic adenoma. The Laryngoscope. 2002 Dec; 112 (12): 2141 – 54.
 9. Cohen MB, Fisher PE, Holly EA, Ljung BM, Lowhagen T, Bottles K. Fine needle aspiration biopsy diagnosis of mucoepidermoid carcinoma. Statistical analysis. Acta cytological. 1990 Jan. 1; 34(1): 43 – 9.
 10. Rankow RM, Polayer IM. Disease of the salivary glands Philadelphia.
 11. Spiro RH, Huvos AG, Strong EW. Cancer of the parotid gland: a clinicopathologic study of 288 primary cases. The American Journal of Surgery. 1975 Oct 1; 130 (4): 452 – 9.
 12. Abdel-Halim D, Anagnostopoulos D, Angerpointner TA, Bill H, Cass D, Clatworth HW, Crooks J, Ehrenpreis T, Haller JA, Hecker WC, Montagnani CA. Historical aspects of paediatric surgery. Springer Science and Business Media; 2012 Dec.6.
 13. Ellis Gray L, Auclair Paul L and Gnepp Douglas R. Surgical pathology of the Salivary glands. 2nd edition. Philadelphia. W.B. Saunders. 1991; Vol. 25: 61 – 91.
 14. Ellis G, Auclair P, Genppa DR. Surgical Pathology of the Salivary Glands: Volume 25 in the Major Problems in Pathology Series: v. 25. Philadelphia: Saunders; 1991. 594p.
 15. Potdur CG. et. al. Tumours of the parotid Ind J Surg. 1962; 31 : 341-342.
 16. Budharaja SN. et. al. Salivary gland tumours in Pondichery. Ind J surg. 1974; 36: 235-239.
 17. Morgan MN, Mackenzie DH. Tumours of salivary glands. A review of 204 cases with 5-year follow-up. Journal of British Surgery. 1968 Apr; 55(4): 284-8.
 18. Skolink EM, Friedman M, Becker S, Sissonn GA, Keyes GR. Tumors of the major salivary glands. The Laryngoscope. 1977 Jun; 87(6): 843-61.
 19. Khazanchi RK, Saha SS, Mital D, Patir R, Dhawan IK. Tumors De Parotid Gland – A Review of 88 Patients and Current Methods of Treatment. Indian Journal of Cancer. 1988 Mar.; 25(1): 1 – 6.
 20. Renehan A, Gleave EN, Hancock BD, Smith P, McGurk M. Long-term follow-up of over 1000 patients with salivary gland tumours treated in a single centre. Journal of British Surgery. 1996 Dec.; 83 (12): 1750 – 4.
 21. Everson JW. Salivary gland tumors, a review of 2410 cases with particular reference to histologic types, sites, age and sex distribution. J. Pathol 1985; 461: 51 – 58.
 22. Fenn AS, et. al. Salivary gland tumors. Ind J of Cancer. 1982; 44: 101 – 104.
 23. Dept. of Pathology. Seth GS Medical College, and KEM Hospital, Mumbai.
 24. Spiro RH. Salivary neoplasms: Overview of a 35 years' experience with 2,807 patients. Head & neck surgery. 1986 Jan.; 8 (3): 177 – 84.
 25. Eversole LR. Histogenic classification of salivary tumours. Arch Pathol. 1971; 92: 433 – 43.
 26. Ellis GL, Corio RL. Acinic cell adenocarcinoma. A clinicopathologic analysis of 294 cases. Cancer. 1983 Aug 1; 52(3): 542 – 9.
 27. Bhatia A. Fine needle aspiration cytology in the diagnosis of mass lesions of the salivary gland. Indian Journal of Cancer. 1993 Mar. 1; 30(1): 26 – 30.
 28. Frable MA, Frable WJ. Fine-Needle aspiration biopsy revisited. The Laryngoscope. 1982 Dec.; 92(12): 1414-8.
 29. Spiro RH, Koss LG, Hajdu SI, Strong EW. Tumors of minor salivary origin. Cancer. 1973 Jan; 31(1) : 117
a. 29.
 30. Leverstein H, Van Der Wal Je, Tiwari RM, Tobi H, Van Der Waal I, Mehta DM, Snow GB. Malignant epithelial parotid gland tumors: analysis and results in 65 previously untreated patients. Journal of British Surgery. 1998 Sept; 85(9): 1267 – 72.
 31. Sousa J, De Sa O. Salivary gland tumours: An analysis of 62 cases. Indian Journal of Cancer. 2001 Mar. 1; 38(1): 38 – 45.
 32. Debets JM, Munting JD. Parotidectomy for parotid tumours: 19 years' experience from the Netherlands. Journal of British Surgery. 1992 Nov.; 79 (11): 1159 – 61.
 33. Owen ER, Banerjee AK, Kissin M, Kark AE. Complications of parotid surgery: the need for selectivity Journal of British Surgery. 1989 Oct; 76 (10): 1034-5.